

A SYSTEMIC METAPHOR OF MULTI-AGENT COORDINATION IN LIVING SYSTEMS

Uwe M. Borghoff¹, Paolo Bottoni^{2*}, Piero Mussio², Remo Pareschi¹

¹ Rank Xerox Research Centre, Grenoble Laboratory
6, chemin de Maupertuis. F-38240 Meylan, France
{borghoff,pareschi}@grenoble.rxc.xerox.com

² Dipartimento di Scienze dell' Informazione, Univ. Roma
Via Salaria 113. I-00198 Roma, Italy
{bottoni,mussio}@dsi.uniroma1.it

KEYWORDS

Graphical simulation environment, simulation software tool, agent-based coordination, artificial life, systemic metaphor.

ABSTRACT

Living systems provide a good metaphor for the coordination of autonomous agents managing tasks according to their role in the system. The study of such systems from the point of view of General Systems Theory would benefit from computational experimentation. This paper proposes an agent-based methodology for system modeling as well as computational tools to develop and test system models.

Biological problems are general enough to provide a metaphor by which one can model several problems in coordinating multi-agent behavior. We show that systems theory and the study of living systems provide insight in the various problems of multi-agent coordination, and that this insight produces computational models where we can express complex coordination patterns involving highly-specialized agents, particularly those cases where the issue of sharing limited resources is crucial.

INTRODUCTION

The cybernetics flavor of the term *open systems* can also be applied to a living (or artificial) system that can interact with the environment by receiving inputs produced by the environment, outside of the control of the system itself, and by producing output directed towards the environment. Agent-based approaches are gaining currency in the programming of such open systems, in particular, for such tasks as simulating the way systems behave and characterizing interactions with the simulated models (Pietrogrande *et al.* 1990).

On the other hand, researchers working with concurrency have been among the first to discover and to evangelize the power of the *open system metaphor* (Hewitt 1985). The suitability of such metaphor for the general problem of coordination of software agents has been recently pointed out in (Ciancarini 1990).

In this paper, we develop a computational approach to the modeling of open systems based on General Systems Theory. The approach derives from experiences in simulation of living system

behavior and provides sophisticated insight into different coordination issues. The approach is based on the notion of local environment, allowing the formulation of an abstract model of group communication which reflects characteristics of different existing models for communication.

We are influenced by models based on generative (or associative) communication, generally realized by data spaces (*e.g.* *Swarm* (Roman and Cunningham 1990), *Linda* (Carriero and Gelernter 1990), *CHAM* (Berry and Boudol 1990), *Gamma* (Banâtre and Métayer 1990), *UNITY* (Chandy and Misra 1988)), and by models based on message passing, *e.g.* *Actors* (Agha 1986). The *LO* model (Andreoli *et al.* 1992) also combines both aspects: intra-pool communication realizes a form of active reading, by applying rewrite rules to resources as they become available, while inter-pool communication is based on actual delivery of new resources to an agent from the outside.

Another feature of our proposed model is the interplay between asynchronous communication and synchronization with an external global synchronizer. In the applications presented here, this role is played by user interactions in a visual interactive environment, or by a global clock simulating the modeling time in the simulation of some immunological phenomena.

In general, the model applies to situations in which individual agents must have completed certain lines of actions before the general process is allowed to progress. This is reflected in the characteristics of the group by considering that the composition of the group may vary only after completion of activities. Naturally, this structure imposes a constraint on message delivery (Arcelli *et al.* 1995; Borghoff *et al.* to appear), limiting the set of agents to which a message can be actually sent (see also (Andreoli *et al.* 1994a; Andreoli *et al.* 1995; Andreoli *et al.* 1996)). Coordination in a complex system is thus realized through the presence of several address or message spaces.

The paper is organized as follows. First, the characteristics of the systemic metaphor are discussed. A model for group communication, centered on the notion of local environment, is motivated. Two examples are given. One for development and management of visual user interfaces, and one for simulation of living systems. A case study in simulation is illustrated in detail. The systems were developed according to the systemic metaphor and define two different implementations of the concept of local environment. We conclude by discussing some aspects of the computational model originated from the notion of local environment.

*Work done while visiting the Rank Xerox Research Centre at Grenoble.

A SYSTEMIC METAPHOR

Living systems are modeled as open systems where several processes may be concurrently active. Such processes constrain each other so as to maintain the identity of the system until it terminates. From a mathematical point of view, the notion of system identity is given by the capability of the system to keep its state within a *viability domain* (Aubin 1990). A system is viable if there exist trajectories originating from a state in its viability domain which remain in this domain. A living system maintains its identity through changes as long as it is able to find such trajectories in its state space. Under this approach, the state of the system is determined by the activity of swarms of agents of different kinds (e.g. cells, antibodies, or antigens) that may cooperate or compete, while pursuing different lines of metabolic behavior. Agents act autonomously, *i.e.* they may become active even in the absence of external events, or may select ways to respond to such events on the basis of their local state. Thus, system survival comes from the coordination of autonomous activities. In general, there is no centralized controller to impose coordination; rather, coordination emerges through local communication among special agents with the role of supporting and restricting communication. Inter-agent communication is itself constrained by the overall characteristics of the environments where agents operate (e.g. vascular system, tissues, internal organs, etc.). The anatomical structures and the physical dimensions of the organism/environment act as selectors of the agents that are able to communicate with each other at a given time.

It is interesting to look at how this metaphor compares with the notion of coordination in computer science. From a programming language perspective, coordination has been defined “the process of building programs by gluing together active pieces” (Carriero and Gelernter 1990). More recently, the term has been given a more *pro-active* reading where coordinators are viewed as specialized agents responsible for effectively managing the interactions among heterogeneous objects (Andreoli *et al.* 1994b).

From a systemic standpoint, we could similarly view coordination as “the process of maintaining a complex system in the viability domain by making agents communicate properly”. This definition is also comprehensive of a view of coordination as “managing dependencies between activities” recently proposed to sum up the different meanings of the word *coordination* from different fields such as physiology, social science, and computer science (Malone and Crowston 1994). Notice that, by tuning the viability requirements differently, this definition applies equally well to the modeling of living systems and to the design of artificial systems. For instance, as death is a fact of life, living systems must be permitted to abandon the viability domain and die. By contrast, as robustness is a requirement for practical use, an artificial system (e.g. a user interface management system) must maximize its capability of intercepting events leading to its own failure, so as to stay within the viability domain and survive.

Our current research addresses these issues through the computational realization of systems as objects, through the definition of a group-based model of communication reflecting the concept of network of systems, and through the definition of the conditions under which distributed control can maintain survival.

In this paper, however, we focus mainly on coordination through group communication, and on some important aspects of the correspondence between systems and objects.

Coordination through Group Communication

The notion of mobility can be abstractly conceived as the possibility that an agent interacts with different sets of agents dynamically, *i.e.* the particular local environment it belongs to at a given time. According to the activities it has to take part to, and according to the kind of messages it is interested in, an agent can belong to several local environments. In particular, a local environment can be defined in terms of the type of messages relevant to an activity (Bianchi *et al.* 1993). Modeling the local environment itself by an object would allow enforcing a form of synchronization on the concurrent activity of agents in the same group as discussed in (Frolund and Agha 1993). The space of local environments can be described as a completely connected directed graph. An edge labeled by “ ∞ ” indicates that no direct connection exists between the source and the target node. By extension, this can be used to represent dynamic networks of agents, where nodes representing agents in the same local environment are connected by links labeled with 0. Different degrees of dynamicity in the topology of the network are compatible with this view:

- in a *fixed topology*, each agent communicates with a fixed set of agents occupying the nodes in a graph whose label is different from ∞ ;
- in a *controlled topology*, labels in the graph may vary under the control of well-defined local rules;
- in a *variable topology*, connections vary in an unpredictable way under the influence of external events, e.g. new agents can be created and dynamically connected with existing agents.

All these forms of dynamicity can be modeled as modifications of the edge labels. Incidentally, this provides a direct representation of the process through which agents come to communicate with new agents as in *Actors* (Agha 1986) or in the π -calculus (Milner *et al.* 1989). Coordination languages aim at a seamless integration of different styles of communication over a network. In the weak sense of making all messages potentially known to all the agents in the computation, this has usually been tackled by assuming a basic form of communication which is as little committing as possible, namely broadcasting (Andreoli *et al.* 1992). Other forms of communication, such as multicasting, point-to-point, or negotiations can then be easily implemented on top of this basic mechanism (Borghoff 1994). Agents select and, possibly, compete for messages which satisfy given properties. With some dissimilarities, the systemic concept of local environment fits with this approach. Here the notion of group is central: agents within the same group, the local environment, can select the relevant messages in an associative way. This kind of group-based property-driven communication may specialize into point-to-point communication, as agents “get to know each other” and thus develop special relationships for given tasks. This amounts to creating a possibly temporary privileged communication channel between two or more agents where private communication can occur.

The task of setting up such a channel is carried out by the involved agents themselves, by exchanging such information as the naming of the channel, the pattern of communication, or the quality of communication.

VISUAL USER INTERFACES

In this section, we give a proof of concept for the system model, especially the local environments, in the context of so-called *co-operative visual environments (CVE)*.

Cooperative visual environments are computer-based environments in which users may cooperate with a system to adapt its presentation and interaction forms to their needs (Bianchi *et al.* 1993). Cooperative visual environments allow users to define different views for the observation of the results of a computational process, and relations among computational processes. In this line, it is essential to uncouple the management of application processes from that of their views, and these from the actual materialization of the outputs corresponding to these views on a suitable surface, *e.g.* the computer screen. On the other hand, run-time adaptation of the interface is feasible if management of relations is treated separately from the definition of processes. This approach is consistent with the principle of *separation of concerns*, proposed in fields as diverse as communication among modules and management of concurrency. Three typologies of agents, organized in three corresponding layers, have been defined:

- *executive agents* managing the application;
- *observer agents* managing the formatting of data for presentation and decoding user interactive commands and data entry;
- *surface agents* managing the materialization of the formatted data and providing support to capture user interactions.

Several surface agents may be composed into a so-called *network agent* defining the surface organization of the interface, and reflecting the logical organization of activities to be performed. Each typology of agents is realized by a corresponding typology of objects. This logical organization is described in detail in (Bottoni *et al.* 1994b).

Communication among Objects

All objects communicate by exchanging messages in a way constrained by the existence of a so-called *communication relation*. Three types of relations are used to establish links for communication among objects:

- *one-to-one* relations are used for inter-layer links;
- *one-to-many* relations are the building blocks for composition links;
- *many-to-many* relations are the basis for action links as well as data links.

Inter-layer links (*i.e.*, from surface objects to observer objects and from observer objects to executive objects) and *composition links* (*i.e.* relating surface objects in a network object, such as a window to the corresponding icons) are implemented as pointers in the sender object such that messages can be directly sent from the sender to the receiver. Out of this scheme we identify two other kinds of links: *action links* and *data links*.

An action link spans from surface objects to surface objects whereas a data link may connect objects within the same layers. An action link is used to replicate an event generated in a certain part of the surface to other surface objects. An action link is

labeled with a name *msg* of a message. This label identifies a local environment, *i.e.*, if *msg* is sent within this environment, all members will receive the message via group broadcast. In this way, a set of concurrent activities may be started by a single interaction. An action link may be enabled or disabled during the execution of a task.

A data link, on the other hand, is labeled with a name *attr* of a given attribute. This label identifies the relation between a sender object and a set of receiver objects which are interested in the data specified by *attr*. This link can be used by an object either to request data of type *attr* from other agents, or to communicate to other objects the current value of *attr*. Thus, it allows the triggering of actions upon state changes. In this way, objects can cooperate during execution. Similarly to an action link, a data link may be enabled or disabled.

Figure 1: A schematization of the structure of a relation.

During execution, objects can be active or not. Therefore we also record the current state of an object in order to notify only active objects. Both data and action links are stored in the state variable of so-called *coordinator* agents; the data structure defining such relations is shown in Fig. 1. It is worth pointing out that the interactions to adapt the interface can result in the creation or suppression of agents and relations, or in the insertion and deletion of agents in a relation. Having these links managed separately allows for the dynamic reconfiguration without objects having to know the addresses of the objects with which they will have to communicate.

Coordination of Concurrent Activities

The coordinator agents are always active whenever cooperative visual environments are being executed. Moreover, they manage the links to properly dispatch messages. Messages circulating in a cooperative visual environment have the following format: $msg(op, sender, params)$ where *op* is used by the receiving objects to select the operation to perform in response, *sender* is the object which originated the message, and *params* are optional arguments to specialize the response. We adopt the conventional notation that the first element in *params* can be used as the address of an agent in case the sender knows it. Messages are sent directly from a sender to a receiver if the sender possesses an inter-layer or composition link to the receiver. In all other cases, a coordinator is called for an action. The coordinator is able to provide a set of addresses contained in a data link to route action messages and to broadcast messages.

1. Addresses are provided when a message to the coordinator has the required format, *i.e.* an object needs to know the

names of the objects with which it has the data-link relation. The coordinator identifies the set of addresses of the active objects that are part of the relation.

2. Action messages are routed by the coordinator whenever an object invokes the concurrent activation of other objects with which it has a relation. The coordinator intercepts an event generated in an interaction and uses a local method to send a copy of the message to all the active objects of the corresponding action link.
3. Messages can also be directly broadcast to all agents having a data-link relation. Similar to the behavior of an action link, the coordinator checks the names of the agents having the data-link relation with the sender and forwards all messages to these agents. This is typically used by an agent to let related agents know that the value of a certain attribute has changed.

The possibility is also envisaged to define action and data links as objects with a state variable containing the corresponding data structure of links, and having the coordinator delegate to them the correct management of the relevant messages. The advantage of this protocol over flat broadcast is that not all agents need to react to a message even if they have methods that could be triggered. In contrast, only those agents are activated which belong to the given relation. It is interesting to note that this is realized without the need of every agent to store the names of all other agents with which it is in the given relation. The agents are possibly coming to know each other on an *as-needed* basis.

Since dynamic modification is possible, the composition of a relation is not guaranteed to be stable for an entire interactive session. New agents may be defined, others may be suppressed, others may change their activity state. Nevertheless, it is guaranteed that no change occurs during an interaction round involving the relation itself. That is to say that no relation is modified by using the relation itself. This is achieved by defining a special environment for the definition of interfaces in which a user works on the representation of its interface; thus realizing a meta-architecture (Mussio *et al.* 1992). Therefore, even if an agent comes to know names of other objects through the use of the data link, the validity of this set of names as response to the initial request is limited to an interaction round, *i.e.* to the activities which are realized between two user commands.

An example for a cooperative visual environment is illustrated in Fig. 2. It shows the user interface in which an expert in biopsy interpretation can explore features of an image. Two windows are devoted to the visualization of (not necessarily related) images, and connected to observer agents on different executive objects; the third is devoted to the visualization of the histogram and connected to an observer agent on the histogram executive object. The two image executive agents are able to get images from a data base and to provide data on pixels in them. The histogram executive agent is able to compute the histogram of any image. The two observer agents for images are connected by data links so that the user may locate corresponding pixels with the cursor. This data link is made at the observer level and not at the execution level, since it is the observer agent which has the control of the portion of image which is currently displayed. The histogram executive agent is connected by a data link with the first image executive agent, so that it computes the histogram of the image currently in question.

In the given case the user is exploring the grey levels of an image to identify the characteristics of a segmentation. The window on the left shows a liver biopsy at grey levels, and the window in the lower right corner shows its histogram. Each time a new image is loaded in the left window, observer and surface agents calculate and present the corresponding histogram as well as a related image (displayed in the upper right corner of the window). This related image is the result of a segmentation of the original image, highlighting possible nuclei and membranes. The observer agents for these images are linked so that the cursor is located at the same pixels in both images. The current position of the cursors and the grey level of the corresponding pixel are shown in the white bar under the images and the histogram. Each time the cursor is moved in one window, position data are sent to the peer observer agent to synchronize the cursors.

SIMULATION OF BIOLOGICAL SYSTEMS

In this section, we illustrate how the systemic metaphor together with the system model, especially the coordination features, can be applied to the simulation of living systems.

A computational model and a “Language for Simulation of Biological Experiments”, called LiSEB from its Italian acronym, evolving from the systemic approach have been developed to allow simulations based on the definition of autonomous agents moving and interacting within so-called *structured habitats*, *i.e.* sub-networks of local environments sharing some common properties (*e.g.* in the human organism, the vascular system, the tissues, and the internal organs). The language, as presented in (Bottoni *et al.* 1994a), provides primitives for defining the autonomous behaviors of agents and for communication mediated by the diffusion of messages in local environments.

In LiSEB, all the entities that a modeler can identify are defined as agents and realized as objects, be they individual elements or habitats, or even structures within these habitats. Structures are called *spaces of encounters* and model the biological artifacts constraining the possibility of interaction during a time interval in the simulation. Agents modeling individual entities can migrate from one space of encounters to another and from one habitat to another through specific spaces of encounters constituting the interface between habitats. A particular management of simulation time has been defined. LiSEB has been tested by developing programs for the simulation of phenomena related to Cryoglobulinemia pathology (Bottoni *et al.* 1994b).

A Case Study

Cryoglobulinemia (Meltzer *et al.* 1966) is a pathology producing several effects in different subsystems of the human organism (liver, kidneys, etc.) including the inflammatory phenomena of the peripheral tissues, *e.g.* a rash. It may be diagnosed through clinical exams because a peculiar phenomenon is observable when a sample of plasma is frozen, *viz* the formation of a precipitate formed by immunocomplexes. A model has been proposed (Pietrogrande *et al.* 1990) according to which this pathology is a consequence of an overproduction of immunocomplexes. Several experiments have been devised and realized using LiSEB in which different phenomena involved in immunocomplex formation according to the model were simulated. Immunocomplexes result from the aggregation of antibodies (*Ab*) and antigens (*Ag*). This aggregation

IMAGE EXPLORATION

Figure 2: A page of a CVE for image interpretation.

occurs on the basis of chemical and structural affinity. In particular, links between entities occur at specific binding sites on their surfaces. Since *Ab-Ag* aggregation may be not stable, immunocomplex agents may disaggregate and their original components are again free to interact with other agents. Immunocomplexes, in turn, may aggregate other antigens and antibodies on their own sites. The presence of *rheumatoid factor* also allows bridges to be formed between immunocomplexes, so that heavier immunocomplexes can be formed. Again, these immunocomplexes can disaggregate. As an example of the realized simulations, an experiment is described in which a simplified model of the organism is used and the inflammatory phenomena at the tissue-level are observed.

Figure 3: A schematization of the habitats and their relations in simulation of the inflammatory phenomena in Cryoglobulinemia.

In Fig. 3, three habitats are identified in which different kinds

of agents interact:

1. the immune system, producing antibodies and rheumatoid factor (*RF*) by employing some external substances in reaction to the presence of *antigenic stimuli* (*AgS*) in the organism;
2. the circulatory system, in which antibodies from the immune system interact with antigens to form immunocomplexes *IC* which can migrate to the peripheral tissues; *complement proteins* (*C*) interfere with this process causing the disaggregation of an immunocomplex and the reactivation of the original components. As usual, *ES* and *RBC* stand for external substances and red blood cells, respectively.
3. the peripheral tissues, in which pores filter the income of an immunocomplex according to their size and in which phagocytes (*Ph*) may eliminate an immunocomplex.

Apart from reactions based on affinity, non-specific reactions may occur too. For example, phagocytes attack an immunocomplex irrespective of the composition of their binding sites and destroy them. Usually, peripheral tissues are protected by pores against the intrusion of immunocomplexes from the blood. In a healthy organism, pores are usually small and block immunocomplexes almost completely. If the production of immunocomplexes

increases, however, there may be a large number of immunocomplexes with small size in the blood and several of them can pass through the pores. They are eliminated by phagocytes, but as their number increases more phagocytes are needed. Besides, any phenomenon of elimination of an immunocomplex by a phagocyte is connected to modifications in the electro-chemical equilibrium of the phagocyte membrane. The subsequent diffusion of substances in the habitat causes an inflammatory process in which pores dilate to an extent where more immunocomplexes can penetrate the tissues, worsening the inflammation. In the proposed model, inflammation in Cryoglobulinemia is therefore due to an increase in the number of an immunocomplex of small size, as a result of an overproduction of antibodies by the immune system, which itself depends on some error in its regulatory mechanism. In the proposed simulation, the level of inflammation is therefore measured by the activity of phagocytes eliminating immunocomplexes. In Fig. 4, a set of spaces of encounters in the tissues is seen as the interface with the circulatory systems. Pores are modeled as immobile agents located in these spaces.

Legend:

Figure 4: A schematization of the initial state of the Peripheral tissues in the simulation of inflammation.

Communication among Agents

In LiSEB, messages are regarded as the means an agent has to manifest its influence on its local environment and the other objects present in it. The message passing mechanism therefore realizes broadcast. At the beginning of each time step in the global simulation time, agents deposit messages in the mailbox of the space of encounters representing their local environment. All other agents in the same local environment are allowed to access the contents of the mailbox to assess which messages they may extract. The emergence of privileged communication channels among agents requires that messages, besides the identity of their addressee (which can be generic in the case of broadcast messages), are piggybacked with the identity of the sender, so that the sender can become an acquaintance of the receiver. The structure of a message is therefore as shown below, where

- G is a set of identifiers of objects,
- TY_M is a set of message types,
- $loc : G \rightarrow G$ is a function associating with each agent the agent representing its local environment,
- A is the set of attributes of the sending object, and
- $D(a)$ is the domain of the attribute $a \in A$.

In particular, we have:

$$msg = \langle sender, type, receivers, pos, attr, values, t \rangle \quad (1)$$

where

- $sender \in G$ is the name of the sending agent;
- $type \in TY_M$ denotes the type of message;
- $receivers \in P(G) \cup \{\text{"all"}\}$, *i.e.* a message can be addressed to a specific set of agents, including the sender itself, or to all the possible receivers;
- $pos := loc(sender)$, a message can be read only within the same local environment as the sender;
- $attr \in P(A)$, indicates which attributes are contained in the message;
- $values$ indicates the values these attributes assume: for each $a_i \in attr$, it contains a value $v \in D(a_i)$;
- $t \in T$ represents the time at which the message becomes readable by its receivers.

Spaces of encounters make any message available to all of its correct recipients, by letting them explore the contents of their mailbox. Spaces of encounters also mark any deposited message with the indication of the agents which have already read it, and delete a message when all correct recipients have either read it or the time of its validity has expired. Each space of encounters keeps the size $pop(\text{Number}, \text{Time})$ of its residing population updated and makes sure that all agents have issued a manifestation of their state before letting other agents react to them.

Agents have two forms of reading, reminiscent of the operations *in* and *rd* in *Linda* (Carriero and Gelernter 1990): *browsing*, when they just assess the presence of a message, and *extracting*, when they actually use the content of the message. An agent can extract a message only once, but the message remains in the space of encounters available to agents which have not extracted it yet.

Reading is therefore seen as an active process on the part of the agent. Point-to-point communication can arise if the agent is able to recognize that some messages influence its activity and dismiss others as irrelevant. Agents can then select their privileged communication partners through the following scheme:

1. An agent issues a communication, *i.e.* introduces in the space of encounters a message corresponding to a manifestation of components of its own state.
2. An agent receives analogous messages from the other agents.
3. An agent singles out, according to some internal rule, the (possibly empty) set of agents having relevance (either positive or negative) to its goals.

4. An agent starts an action consequent to the identification of the set of influential agents. This action may involve some form of direct communication with them and the issue of more specific messages.

In this process, activities 1 and 2 can use associative communication in which receivers are not known to the sender and reception is based on the relevance of the communication to the current state of the agent. Activities 3 and 4 can instead give origin to direct forms of communication, if an agent is able to select its partner (or partners, where appropriate) in the communication and to produce communication acts whose results are meant to be sent only to the elected partners.

This pattern of communication is common to several situations and is reminiscent of the announcement-bid-award scheme used as a model for the allocation of resources or the assignment of tasks (Smith and Davis 1981).

Behavior of Agents

Whenever concurrent activities have to be performed by a set of distributed agents, the computation of the states they reach at the end of the steps and of the outputs they emit requires the exchange of messages. These messages have no biological interpretation but only a computational meaning. The management of all these activities is performed exploiting a stack recording the names of actions they still have to perform to complete the computation at hand. Note that the agent attributes, the set of available actions and methods, the messages sent and received, and the stack constitute the memory of the agent, *i.e.* its state.

To simulate the immunocomplex formation process in the circulatory system, antibodies, antigens, and immunocomplexes are defined as agents whose state variable contains their binding sites (for more details see (Celada and Seiden 1992)). At each new time step of the global simulation time, each agent deposits in its local environment the composition of its sites, reads site composition of other agents in the same local environment, and selects the most affine agents from other classes to form immunocomplex agents. Conflicts due to equal affinity with more than one agent are resolved by the use of an additional *strength*-variable stating the number of binding sites (each with the same characteristics) an agent actually presents on its surface. Remaining conflicts are resolved non-deterministically. Formed immunocomplexes are allowed to migrate to the tissues. To model aggregation and disaggregation of immunocomplexes, a new typology of objects, called *composed objects* has been defined. A composed object is characterized by having in its state variable a representation of the state of the original components and by methods that allow to disaggregate and restore the original objects.

In this model, antigens and antibodies act symmetrically by reading messages issued by agents of the complementary type and selecting the strongest agent as the affine ones. Phagocytes, for example, look for manifestations of immunocomplexes and compete to eliminate them. The elimination of big immunocomplexes can also involve forms of cooperation among phagocytes. Upon receiving messages from phagocytes, immunocomplexes can avoid being eliminated if no phagocyte is sufficiently strong or commit to the phagocyte with the greatest strength.

An infection has been simulated in which a constant number of antigens enters the organism for an initial period. In the simulation, the immune system reacts by generating antibodies which react with antigens to form immunocomplexes.

Fig. 5 shows the relative presence of these agents in the circulatory system until 30 simulation steps after the end of the *immission* of antigens. It can be observed that the production of antibodies by the immune system causes an initial excess of these agents, which then decreases as antigens are eliminated. Immunocomplexes produced by the aggregation of antigens and antibodies first increase and then, as no antigens are input from the outside – and the existing ones have been captured by antibodies –, decreases until almost all immunocomplexes have been eliminated. The activity of phagocytes in the tissues are an indication of the inflammatory process. It starts to increase as more immunocomplexes are produced and migrate to the tissues, but persists well after the antigens have ceased to be present, as long as there are immunocomplexes which have migrated in the tissues.

All results obtained in our simulation have been considered to be in accordance with experiments reported in the relevant literature.

DISCUSSION

Based on the systemic metaphor, we gave two examples of possible application areas in open systems. We illustrated the development and management of visual user interfaces, and, in more detail, focussed on the simulation of living systems. A real-life case study of the Cryoglobulinemia pathology was introduced. Both examples were developed according to the concept of local environment.

In the proposed examples, a model for coordination emerges which can be summarized as follows: agents communicate by sending messages which are read by all the other agents in a communication relation with the sending agent. This relation can be dynamically established from the outside, or can be defined according to properties of the sending agent. Reception of the message is guaranteed to any agent in the relation by the existence of special coordinator agents supporting representations of the relation. In the case of cooperative visual environments, the communication relation is managed by agents defining the address space of the relation. It is interesting to see how the management of agent names in the spaces of encounters could be realized in the same way as in cooperative visual environments by defining coordinator agents with link information. Since their composition is much more variable than in the case of cooperative visual environments, however, the implementation as agents providing a message space is more convenient. The effect is realized by distributing to each agent knowledge about its position and having changes of position explicitly notified to the spaces.

Some generalizations can be drawn from the proposed models. The idea of restricting communication to subsets of agents as long as they have completed some threads of activities can be applied also in other fields, *e.g.* versioning of information. Furthermore, the idea of forming temporary aggregations with completely new properties and capabilities enables the formation of teams and committees. The main interest of the proposed approach is that coordination patterns emerge from local mechanisms only (Kahn and Miller 1989).

To sum up, systems theory and the study of living systems helped us to get insight in the problems of multi-agent coordination. With the produced computational models we were able to express complex coordination patterns involving multiple autonomous agents in real-life settings.

Figure 5: Simulation results of the relative presence of agents (LiSEB screen shot).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Thanks are due to Maurizio Pietrogrande of the Centro Sudi Medicina Teoretica for proposing the model of Cryoglobulinemia and for helping in the experimentation with LiSEB. We are grateful to Steve Freeman for the careful reading of this paper.

REFERENCES

- G. A. Agha. *Actors: A Model of Concurrent Computation in Distributed Systems*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1986.
- J.-M. Andreoli, P. Ciancarini, and R. Pareschi. "Interaction Abstract Machines". In G. A. Agha, A. Yonezawa, and P. Wegner, editors, *Research Directions in Concurrent Object-Oriented Programming*, pages 257–280. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1992.
- J.-M. Andreoli, U. M. Borghoff, and R. Pareschi. "Constraint-Based Knowledge Brokers". In H. Hong, editor, *Proc. 1st Int. Symp. on Parallel Symbolic Computation (PASCO '94)*, pages 1–11, Hagenberg/Linz, Austria, September 1994. Lecture Notes Series in Computing 5, Singapore, New Jersey, London, Hong Kong: World Scientific.
- J. M. Andreoli, H. Gallaire, and R. Pareschi. "Objects Meet Rules: From Communication to Coordination through Declarativity". In *Proc. Object-World Germany*, Frankfurt, Germany, September 1994.
- J.-M. Andreoli, U. M. Borghoff, R. Pareschi, and J. H. Schlichter. "Constraint Agents for the Information Age". *J. Universal Computer Science*, 1(12):762–789, December 1995. Electronic version available at http://hyperg.iicm.tu-graz.ac.at/Cjucs_root.
- J.-M. Andreoli, U. M. Borghoff, and R. Pareschi. "The Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker Model: Semantics, Implementation and Analysis". *J. Symbolic Computation*, 1996.
- F. Arcelli, U. M. Borghoff, F. Formato, and R. Pareschi. "Tuning Constraint-Based Communication in Distributed Problem Solving". In *Proc. 1st Int. Workshop on Concurrent Constraint Programming (CCP '95)*, Venice, Italy, May 1995.
- J. P. Aubin. *Viability Theory*. Birkhauser, 1990.
- J.-P. Banâtre and D. Le Métayer. "The Gamma Model and its Discipline of Programming". *Science of Computer Programming*, 15:55–77, 1990.
- G. Berry and G. Boudol. "The Chemical Abstract Machine". In *Proc. 17th ACM SIGACT/SIGPLAN Annual Symp. on Principles of Programming Languages*, pages 81–94, San Francisco, CA, 1990.
- N. Bianchi, P. Bottoni, P. Mussio, and M. Protti. "Cooperative Visual Environments for the Design of Effective Visual Systems". *J. of Visual Languages and Computing*, 4:357–381, 1993.
- U. M. Borghoff, R. Pareschi, F. Arcelli, and F. Formato. "Constraint-Based Protocols for Distributed Problem Solving". *Science of Computer Programming*, to appear.
- U. M. Borghoff. "LOKIT: A Toolkit for Building Distributed Collaborative Applications". Technical Report CT-002, Rank Xerox Research Centre, Grenoble Lab., France, May 1994.
- P. Bottoni, M. Mariotto, and P. Mussio. "LiSEB: A Language for Modeling Living Systems with APL2". In *Proc. APL '94*, 25:1, pages 7–16. APL Quote Quad, 1994.
- P. Bottoni, M. Mariotto, P. Mussio, and M. Pietrogrande. "Emergent Behaviours in Populations of Autonomous Agents". In *Proc. Europ. Workshop on Artificial Emergence*, May 1994.
- N. Carriero and D. Gelernter. *How To Write Parallel Programs. A First Course*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1990.
- F. Celada and P. Seiden. "A Computer Model for Cellular Interaction in the Immune System". *Immunology Today*, 13(2):56–62, 1992.
- K. M. Chandy and J. Misra. *Parallel Program Design: A Foundation*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1988.
- P. Ciancarini. "Coordination Languages for Open System Design". In *Proc. IEEE Conf. on Computer Languages*, pages 120–129. Los Alamitos, CA: IEEE Comp. Soc. Press, 1990.
- S. Frolund and G. Agha. "A Language Framework for Multi-Object Coordination". In O. Nierstrasz, editor, *Proc. 7th Conf. on Object-Oriented Programming (ECOOP '93)*, pages 346–360, Kaiserslautern, Germany, 1993. Lecture Notes in Computer Science 707. Berlin, Heidelberg, New York: Springer-Verlag.

- C. Hewitt. "The Challenge of Open Systems". *Byte*, 10(4):223–242, 1985.
- K. Kahn and M. Miller. "Comments on Linda in Context". *Communications of the ACM*, 10(5):1240–1258, 1989.
- T. W. Malone and K. Crowston. "The Interdisciplinary Study of Coordination". *ACM Computing Surveys*, 26(1):87–119, March 1994.
- M. Meltzer, C. Franklin, and K. Elias. "Cryoglobulinemia". *American J. of Medicine*, 40:828, 1966.
- R. Milner, J. Parrow, and D. Walker. "A Calculus of Mobile Processes I & II". Technical Report ECS-LFCS-89-85&86, Dept. of Computer Science, Univ. of Edinburgh, 1989.
- P. Mussio, M. Finadri, P. Gentini, and F. Colombo. "A Bootstrap Technique to Visual Interface Design and Development". *The Visual Computer*, 8(2):75–93, 1992.
- M. Pietrogrande, B. Sagramoso, P. Bottoni, P. Mussio, and N. Dioguardi. "Utilization of Systemic Models for the Study of Pathogenesis, Clinical Picture and Therapy of Diseases. Case Study. Cryoglobulinemia". In V. d'Amato and C. Maccheroni, editors, *Dynamic Analysis of Complex Systems*, pages 274–278, Milano, Italy, 1990. Franco Angeli, Publ.
- G-C. Roman and H. C. Cunningham. "Mixed Programming Metaphors in a Shared Dataspace Model of Concurrency". *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, 16(12):1361–1373, 1990.
- R. G. Smith and R. Davis. "Frameworks for Cooperation in Distributed Problem Solving". *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, 11(1):61–70, 1981.

BIOGRAPHIES

Uwe Borghoff holds B.S., M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in Computer Science from the Technische Universität München, Munich, Germany. In 1993, he was awarded the *venia legendi* in Computer Science. Uwe Borghoff worked for IBM and freelance with IBBG for three years before joining the faculty of Computer Science at the Technische Universität München as Assistant and research scientist in 1986. Since February 1994, he has been senior scientist at the Rank Xerox Research Centre in Grenoble, France. His research interests include language support and protocols for computer-supported collaborative work, and distributed document processing. As project manager, he has devoted his interests to interworking using constraint-based programming techniques, especially to the problem of knowledge brokerage in the world-wide web. Uwe Borghoff is a coauthor of *Computer-Supported Groupwork* (Springer-Verlag 1995), a standard German textbook on the subject, and author of *Catalogue of Distributed File/Operating Systems* (Springer-Verlag 1992). He is an editor of the Journal of Universal Computer Science (J.UCS), and is a member of the ACM, the IEEE, and the German Association of Computer Scientists.

Paolo Bottoni received a Degree in Physics from the University of Milan in 1988 and a Ph.D. in Computer Science from the University of Turin in 1995. He is now a research associate in the Department of Computer Science of the University of Rome "La Sapienza." His research interests evolved from Structural Pattern Recognition to the definition of a model for the specification of emerging activities of populations of communicating agents capable of both autonomous and reactive behavior. He has collaborated to the design of visual interactive environments for image interpretation and simulation of biological systems. He is member of the ACM, IEEE CS, IAPR and AI*IA.

Piero Mussio graduated from Milan Politechnic in 1968. From 1970 to 1983 he was researcher at the Laboratory of Cosmic Physics (LFCTR) of the National Research Council of Italy in Milan. At LFCTR he was Data Reduction Officer in European Collaborations and in charge of the Group of Data Analysis. In 1983 he joined the Department of Physics of Milan University as Associate Professor in Computer Science and responsible of the Image Processing and Interpretation Group. In 1992 he joined the

Department of Information Science of the University "La Sapienza" of Rome. His research interests include visual languages and computing and multiagent environments for visual interaction.

Remo Pareschi leads the research group on Coordination Technologies (CT) at the Rank Xerox Research Centre in Grenoble since September 1993. His responsibilities include the design, implementation and experimentation of software to meet users' needs in networked organizations and to support the management of knowledge in distributed software environments. At the current stage, the CT group is working on innovative tools for process-oriented middleware and for information gathering. Remo Pareschi is also very active in the area of Object Oriented Programming. He has co-chaired an international conference on this subject (ECOOP'94), has acted as programme committee member of several others, and is associate editor of the International Journal of Theory and Practice of Object Systems (TAPOS). More recently, he has investigated the use of constructs from declarative languages, such as rules and constraints, for the management of processes and of knowledge in networked environments. Remo Pareschi was previously Team Leader at the European Computer-Industry Research Centre in Munich, a private research centre owned by the European computer vendors Bull, ICL and Siemens, where he was responsible for the design and implementation of software technologies for concurrent and distributed systems. Before joining the computer industry, he was a research associate with the Department of Computer and Information Sciences of the University of Pennsylvania. He holds degrees from University of Bologna (laurea), University of Texas at Austin (Master's) and University of Edinburgh (Ph.D.).